

Console Applications for Mathematical Functions, EEG Signal Analysis, String Manipulation and Utilities.

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Overview

Applications for calculating (1) *distribution* functions and *bootstrap* estimators (s. Tab. 1; c.f. Schrausser, 2023a, 2024a), (2) various parameters within the framework of psychophysiological EEG measurements (c.f. Schrausser, 2024b), (3) *integral* and *interpolation* (Schrausser, 2023b) and (4) *matrix* parameters (Schrausser, 2023c), s. Tab. 2. Further applications are (5) *string-* and *number- transformation tools* (Schrausser, 2023d) and finally (6) various *console tools* (Schrausser, 2023e), see Tab. 3. For a full *BibTeX* source of the reference list, see Schrausser (2026).

The applications are written in *ANSI-C* (c.f. Gerlach, 2019; Joyce, 2019; Gonzalez-Morris & Horton, 2024), executables were compiled for *MS-DOS* (c.f. Kaier, 1990; Herrmann, 2001).

Certain applications are implemented in the Windows Tools (i) *FunktionWin* (see Schrausser, 2023f, 2025c), (ii) *ThetaWin* (see Schrausser, 2009, 2023g, 2025a) and (iii) *ATINA* (s. Schrausser, 2006). For better comparability, the *original* German-language terms are presented comparatively in *italic* text.

1. ConsoleApp_DistributionFunctions

Console applications for *distribution* functions (c.f. Schrausser, 2023a, 2024a) implemented in *FunktionWin* (see Schrausser, 2023f, 2025c).

The following functions are available:

(1.1.-1.2.) *Binomial* distribution (de Moivre, 1711; Bernoulli, 1713) as a discrete distribution of probability values from frequency ratios of two groups, c.f. Collani and Dräger (2001), Philippou and Antzoulakos (2025), further e.g. Mulholland and Jones (1968a), Altham (1978), Goel and Rodriguez (1987), Velaisamy and Punnen (2001), García-García et al. (2022).

(1.3.) Effect size, *Cohen's d* (Cohen, 1977, 1988, p.20, p.49, 1992), an effect size measure that represents the magnitude of the difference between two group means in standard deviation units. Further works on this topic are given by e.g. Wilcox (2006), Miller et al. (2011), Fritz et al. (2012), Janczyk and Pfister (2013), Peng and Chen (2014), Li (2016), Schäfer and Schwarz (2019), Bowring et al. (2021), Groß and Möller (2023, 2024) and Brandmaier (2025).

(1.4.) Fisher-Snedecor *F*-distribution (Fisher, 1924), a continuous probability distribution for determining significance levels in multigroup and factorial designs, c.f. also David (1949), Patnaik (1949), Zinger (1964), Cacoullos (1965), Stange (1970), Saunders and Moran (1978), Herrmann (1984), Selvin (2014), Brereton (2015) or Chattamvelli and Shanmugam (2021).

(1.5.) *Fisher's exact test* (Fisher, 1922; s. Altham, 1969), *exact hypergeometric* 4-field test, a non-parametric statistical procedure for significance testing of frequency distributions in 2x2 designs, see in this context e.g. Upton (1992), Camilli (1995), Hershberger (2014), Sprent (2025).

(1.6.) *Fisher Z*-transformation (Fisher, 1915), to adjust the distribution of *product moment* correlation coefficients *r* to a *normal* distribution in order to perform valid significance tests, interesting discussions on the topic are given by Hjelm and Norris (1962), Mendoza (1993), Bond and Richardson (2004), Carbonell et al. (2009) or Yang et al. (2013).

(1.7.-1.8.) *Gamma* function Γ (Bernoulli, 1729) to extend the factorial to non-integer arguments (c.f. Borwein & Corless, 2018). The *gamma* integral, or *gamma* value, is also a *central* parameter of the *F*, *t*, and χ^2 distributions implemented here, s. e.g. Gronwall (1918), Rasch (1931), Davis (1959), Magnus et al. (1966a), Saunders and Moran (1978), Batir (2008), Koepf (2014).

(1.9.) *Hypergeometric* distribution (Wallis, 1656) for the calculation of significance levels for frequencies in 2x2 designs, see *Fisher's exact test* above, c.f. Berggren et al. (2000) or Stedall (2005), s. further e.g. Magnus et al. (1966b), Dutka (1984) or Shuster (2014)

(1.10.) *Geometric* distribution (de Montmort, 1713) calculates the probability that event *A* with probability p_A occurs at least once in $r + 1$ attempts, c.f. Sreehari (1983), Zijlstra (1983) or Thomopoulos (2017).

(1.11.) *Poisson* distribution (Poisson, 1837) is generally right-skewed, but approaches with (i) increasing expected number of events λ the *normal* distribution (c.f. Chung, 1974), with (ii) large n and small p the *binomial* distribution, a more detailed insight into this method provide e.g. Rao and Chakravarti (1956), Crow (1958), Haight (1967), Simonton (1978), Jolicoeur (1999), Finkelstein et al. (2025) or Zhang (2025).

(1.12.) Student's *t*-distribution (Lüroth, 1876; Gosset, 1908) to approximate significance levels if sample sizes n are small, it converges to the *normal* distribution as n increases (s. Wang, 2011), c.f. further Cacoullos (1965), Yang et al. (2007), Fonseca et al. (2008), Peña et al. (2009), Grigelionis (2012), Brereton (2015), Li and Nadarajah (2020), Reyes et al. (2021), Kirkby et al. (2024) and Edelman (2025).

(1.13.) χ^2 -distribution (Helmert, 1876) can be derived from the *normal* distribution (c.f. Behnke & Behnke, 2006) and provides significance level determinations for frequency parameters, thus serving as an *approximation for exact* level determination through probability distributions such as *binomial*, *multinomial* or *hypergeometric* (c.f. Camilli, 1995), s. in this context Wilson and Hilferty (1931), Patnaik (1949), Molinari (1977), Hafner (1992), Jolicoeur (1999), Canal (2005), Brereton (2015) and Das (2025).

(1.14.-1.15.) *Normal* distribution (de Moivre, 1738) or *Gaussian* distribution is fundamental to the *central limit theorem*, which states that the means of many independent, identically distributed random variables tend to follow this *normal* distribution, the *basis of inferential statistics*. The *z*-transformation with a mean of $\bar{x} = 0$ and a standard deviation of $s = 1$ yields the *standard normal* distribution, c.f. Behnke and Behnke (2006). See moreover David (1949), Breitenberger (1963), Mulholland and Jones (1968b), Chung (1974), Leaver and Thomas (1974), Thome (1990), Sachs (1993), Massart et al. (1998), von Storch and Zwiers (1999), Stahl (2006), Tóth (2011), Wang (2011), Brereton (2014), Lyon (2014), Bera et al. (2016), Wesolowski and Musselwhite Thompson (2018), Benzon (2021) or Saneii and Doosti (2024).

Theta applications (1.16.-1.23.) generating distributions and *estimators* for several parameters θ (*theta*) within different designs via *bootstrap* method (Efron, 1979, 1981, 1982, res.), with given number of resamples B , where *bootstrap* estimator

$$\hat{\theta}_B = B^{-1} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^B \theta_i^*$$

Implemented in *ThetaWin* (see Schrausser, 2009, 2023g, 2025a); for a deeper and current insight into the *bootstrap* method see e.g. Politis (1998), Bickel and Ren (2001), Horowitz (2001), Wilcox (2001), Machado and Parente (2005), Kleiner et al. (2014), Kenett et al. (2022) or Zuev (2026); furthermore Hall (2003), Politis (2003), Pewsey (2018), Khosravi et al. (2021), Baïllo and Cárcamo (2025), Eidous (2025), Liu (2025) or Zheng and Fan (2025).

1.1. Binomial

$$f(X \leq k|n) = \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{n!}{i! \cdot (n-i)!} \cdot p^i \cdot q^{(n-i)}$$

Usage:

Binomial [p][k][n] [[1]]
 [p] Probability of event A
 [k] n of events A
 [n] n of trials
 [1] (1):full output

1.2. Binomial_T

$$f(X \leq b|b, c) = p = \sum_{i=0}^b \frac{(b+c)!}{i! \cdot (b+c-i)!} \cdot 2^{-i} \cdot 2^{-(b+c-i)}$$

Usage:

Binomial_T [b][c] [[1]]
 [b] Cell count b
 [c] Cell count c
 [1] (1):full output

1.3. Epsilon

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_0}{\hat{\sigma}}$$

Usage:

epsilon [mode][Q0][s][n][e|Q1][p][df] [[x]]
 [mode] (1):Effect-size (2):Theta.1
 [Q0] Theta.0
 [s] Standard deviation
 [n] n of cases
 [e|Q1] Epsilon | Theta.1
 [p] Percent-level (0.000)
 [df] Degrees of freedom n - (.)
 [x] Test value

1.4. F_Function

$$F(F, df_1, df_2) = 1 - p^{\sigma^2} = \int_0^F \frac{\Gamma(\frac{df_1+df_2}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{df_1}{2}) \cdot \Gamma(\frac{df_2}{2})} \cdot \left(\frac{df_1}{df_2}\right)^{\frac{df_1}{2}} \cdot F^{\frac{df_1}{2}-1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{df_1}{df_2} \cdot F\right)^{-\frac{df_1+df_2}{2}} dF$$

Usage:

F_Function [mode][x][n1][n2]
 [mode] (1):Fx=p->F (2):Fy=F->p
 [x] p-value/F-value
 [n1] n1
 [n2] n2

1.5. Fisher_Exact

$$f(X = a|a, b, c, d) = P_0 = \frac{(a+b)! \cdot (c+d)! \cdot (a+c)! \cdot (b+d)!}{(a+b+c+d)! \cdot a! \cdot b! \cdot c! \cdot d!}$$

$$f(X \leq n|a, b, c, d) = p^{\text{exact2}} = \sum_{i=0}^n P_i; P_i \leq P_0$$

Usage:

Fisher_Exact [a][b][c][d] [[1]]
 [a][b][c][d] ... Cell counts a,b,c,d
 [1] (1):full output

1.6. Fisher_Z

$$Z = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \log_e \left(\frac{1+r}{1-r} \right)$$

$$r = \frac{e^{2Z} - 1}{e^{2Z} + 1}$$

Usage:

Fisher_Z [mode][x]
 [mode] (1):r->Z (2):Z->r
 [x] r-value/Z-value

1.7. GAMMA_Function

$$f(x, t) = \Gamma = \int_0^{\infty} t^{x-1} \cdot e^{-t} dt + c$$

Usage:

GAMMA_Function [mode][value]
 [mode] (1):F(x)->[(2):F'()->x
 [value] x / [

1.8. GAMMA

Usage:

GAMMA [n][input][output]
 [n] n of cases
 [input] Input file
 [output] Output file

1.9. Geometric

$$f(X \leq r|p) = \sum_{i=0}^r p \cdot q^i$$

Usage:

Geometric [p][r+1] [[1]]
 [p] Probability of event A
 [r+1] n of trials
 [1] (1):full output

1.10. Hypergeometric

$$f(X \leq k|n, K, N) = \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{\binom{K}{i} \cdot \binom{N-K}{n-i}}{\binom{N}{n}}$$

Usage:

Hypergeometric [k][n][N][K] [[1]]
 [k] n of events A in Sub-Population
 [n] Size of Sub-Population
 [N] Size of Population
 [K] n of events A in Population
 [1] (1):full output

1.11. Poisson

$$f(X \leq k|n, p) = \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{(n \cdot p)^i}{e^{n \cdot p} \cdot i!}$$

Usage:

Poisson [p][k][n] [[1]]
 [p] Probability of event A
 [k] n of events A
 [n] n of trials
 [1] (1):full output

1.12. t_Function

$$F(t, df) = p = \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{\Gamma(\frac{df-1}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{df}{2})} \cdot (df \cdot \pi)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{t^2}{df}\right)^{-\frac{df-1}{2}} dt.$$

Usage:

```
t_Function [mode][x][n]
[mode] ..... (1):Fx=p->t (2):Fy=t->p
[x] ..... p-value/t-value
[n] ..... n of cases
```

1.13. x2_Function

$$F(\chi^2, df) = 1 - p^{\alpha z} = \int_0^{\chi^2} \frac{1}{2^{\frac{df}{2}} \cdot \Gamma(\frac{df}{2})} \cdot (\chi^2)^{\frac{df}{2}-1} \cdot e^{-\frac{\chi^2}{2}} d\chi^2.$$

Usage:

```
x2_Function [mode][x][n]
[mode] ..... (1):Fx=p->x^2 (2):Fy=x^2->p
[x] ..... p-value/x^2-value
[n] ..... n of cases
```

1.14. z_Dichte

$$f(z) = \vartheta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \pi}} \cdot e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}},$$

$$f^{-1}(z) = f(\vartheta) = z = \sqrt{\ln\left(\frac{\vartheta}{\sqrt{(2 \cdot \pi)^{-1}}}\right)^{-2}},$$

$$F(z) = p = \int_{-\infty}^z \vartheta dz.$$

Usage:

```
z_Dichte [mode][value][f]
[mode] ..... (1):fx=z->d (2):fy=d->z (3):fx=z->p
(4):f'p->z (5):f'p->d (6):fy=d->p
[value] ..... z-value/z-density/percent-rank p
[f] ..... (1):z-density function graph
```

1.15. z_Function

Usage:

```
z_Function [mode][x]
[mode] ..... (1):Fx=p->z (2):Fy=z->p
[x] ..... p-value/z-value
```

1.16. Theta

Usage:

```
Theta [sd][min][max][qq][q][v][s][x][g]
[sd] ..... Seed: |0| Timevalue
[min] ..... R Minimum value
[max] ..... R Maximum value
[qq] ..... Theta-Theta/
[q] ..... Theta:
|0| Harmonic mean (HM)
|1| Arithmetic mean (AM)
|2| Sum (SUM)
|3| Standard deviation (SD)
|4| Population variance estimation (VAR)
|5| Product sum (PSM)
|6| Geometric mean (GM)
|7| Schrausser's d (D)
|8| Dvar0 (DV)
[v] ..... n of Theta (v)
[s] ..... n Subpopulations (s)
[x] ..... Test value x
[g] ..... |1| Value range integer
```

1.17. Theta_Q

Usage:

```
Theta_Q [sd][min][max][qq][qp][qs1][qs2][qQ][v][m][n][s][x][g]
[sd] ..... Seed: |0| Timevalue
[min] ..... R Minimum value
[max] ..... R Maximum value
[qq] ..... Theta-Theta/
[qp] ..... Theta P/
[qs1][qs2] ..... Theta S1, S2:
|0| Harmonic mean (HM)
|1| Arithmetic mean (AM)
|2| Sum (SUM)
|3| Standard deviation (SD)
|4| Population variance estim. (VAR)
|5| Product sum (PSM)
|6| Geometric mean (GM)
|7| Schrausser's d (D)
|8| Dvar0 (DV)
[qQ] ..... Theta Q:
|1| Difference
|2| Quotient
|3| Sum
|4| Product
[v] ..... n of Theta P (v)
[m] ..... n of Theta S1 (m)
[n] ..... n of Theta S2 (n)
[s] ..... n Subpopulations (s)
[x] ..... Test value x
[g] ..... |1| Value range integer
```

1.18. Theta_Qv

Usage:

```
Theta_Qv [sd][min][max][qq][qp][qs1][qs2][qQ][qQ][v][n][s][x][g]
[sd] ..... Seed: |0| Timevalue
[min] ..... R Minimum value
[max] ..... R Maximum value
[qq] ..... Theta-Theta/
[qp] ..... Theta P/
[qs1][qs2] ..... Theta S1, S2/
[qQ] ..... Theta Q:
|0| Harmonic mean (HM)
|1| Arithmetic mean (AM)
|2| Sum (SUM)
|3| Standard deviation (SD)
|4| Population variance estim. (VAR)
|5| Product sum (PSM)
|6| Geometric mean (GM)
|7| Schrausser's d (D)
|8| Dvar0 (DV)
[qQ] ..... Theta Theta Q:
|1| Difference
|2| Quotient
|3| Sum
|4| Product
|5| Correlation
|6| Covariance
|7| Coefficient of determination
|8| Redundancy
[v] ..... n of Theta P (v)
[n] ..... n of Theta S1,S2 (n)
[s] ..... n Subpopulations (s)
[x] ..... Test value x
[g] ..... |1| Value range integer
```

1.19. Theta_rQ

Usage:

```
Theta_rQ [sd][min][max][qq][qp][q11][q12][q21][q22][qr1][qr2][qQ][v]
[m][n][s][x][g]
[sd] ..... Seed: |0| Timevalue
[min] ..... R Minimum value
[max] ..... R Maximum value
[qq] ..... Theta-Theta/
[qp] ..... Theta P/
[q11][q12] ..... Theta S11, S12/
[q21][q22] ..... Theta S21, S22:
|0| Harmonic mean (HM)
|1| Arithmetic mean (AM)
|2| Sum (SUM)
|3| Standard deviation (SD)
|4| Population variance estim. (VAR)
|5| Product sum (PSM)
|6| Geometric mean (GM)
|7| Schrausser's d (D)
|8| Dvar0 (DV)
[qr1][qr2] ..... Theta Regressions 1,2/
|1| Correlation (kor)
|2| Covariance (cov)
|3| Coeff. of determination (det)
|4| Redundancy (red)
[qQ] ..... Theta Q:
|1| Difference (Diff)
|2| Quotient (Quot)
|3| Sum (Summ)
|4| Product (Prod)
[v] ..... n of Theta P (v)
```

```

[m] ..... n of Theta S11,S12 (m)
[n] ..... n of Theta S21,S22 (n)
[s] ..... n Subpopulations (s)
[x] ..... Test value x
[g] ..... |1| Value range integer

```

1.20. Theta_S

Usage:

```

Theta_S [sd][min][max][qq][qp][qs][v][m][s] [[x]] [[g]]
[sd] ..... Seed: |0| Timevalue
[min] ..... R Minimum value
[max] ..... R Maximum value
[qq] ..... Theta-Theta:
[qp] ..... Theta P/
[qs] ..... Theta S/
      |0| Harmonic mean (HM)
      |1| Arithmetic mean (AM)
      |2| Sum (SUM)
      |3| Standard deviation (SD)
      |4| Population variance estim. (VAR)
      |5| Product sum (PSM)
      |6| Geometric mean (GM)
      |7| Schrausser's d (D)
      |8| DvarO (DV)
[v] ..... n of Theta P (v)
[m] ..... n of Theta S (m)
[s] ..... n Subpopulations (s)
[x] ..... Test value x
[g] ..... |1| Value range integer

```

1.21. Verteilungsform

Usage:

```

Verteilungsform [min][max][n][s]
[min] ..... Minimum value
[max] ..... Maximum value
[n] ..... n of parameter Theta-sum(x)
[s] ..... n Subpopulations

```

1.22. Verteilungsform_2u

Usage:

```

Verteilungsform_2u [min][max][q][n1][n2][s] [[xd]] [[g]]
[min] ..... Minimum value
[max] ..... Maximum value
[q] ..... Theta:
      |0| Harmonic mean
      |1| Arithmetic mean
      |2| Sum
      |3| Standard deviation
      |4| Population variance estim.
      |5| Product sum
      |6| Geometric mean
      |7| Schrausser's d
      |8| DvarO
[n1] ..... n1 of Theta
[n2] ..... n2 of Theta
[s] ..... n Subpopulations
[xd] ..... Difference test value
[g] ..... |1| Value range integer

```

1.23. Verteilungsform_kor

Usage:

```

Verteilungsform_kor [min][max][q][n][s] [[x]] [[g]]
[min] ..... Minimum value
[max] ..... Maximum value
[q] ..... Theta:
      |1| Pearson Correlation
      |2| Covariance
      |3| Coeff. of determination
      |4| Redundancy
      |5| Regression coefficient axy
      |6| Regression coefficient byx
      |7| Regression coefficient axy
      |8| Regression coefficient byx
[n] ..... n of Theta
[s] ..... n Subpopulations
[x] ..... Test value x
[g] ..... |1| Value range integer

```

Table 1. ConsoleApp distribution functions and bootstrap overview with corresponding functions in SCHRAUSSER-MAT and HP_Prime_MATH (Schrausser, 2022, 2025a, res.).

nr.	Function	SCHRAUSSER-MAT	HP_Prime_MATH
1	Binomial ¹	BNP, BNW	
2	Binomial_T ¹	BN1, BN2	ABT1, BINOM, pzBN, zBN, E01
3	Epsilon ¹	EFG, ANI, BNI, IMB, EFS, OPP	EPSILON, EFG, EFR, E01
4	F_Function ¹	FPW, PFW, PFD	FVTLG, F02, F03Z
5	Fisher_Exact ¹	FX0, FX1, FX2	FX_, z4F, pz4F
6	Fisher_Z ¹	FZR, RFZ	Zcor, rZ, Zr
7	GAMMA_Function ¹	GAMMA, AGAM	
8	GAMMA ¹	IGM	F01z, F04
9	Geometric ¹	GMP, GMW	GMVTLG
10	Hypergeometric ¹	HGP, HGW	
11	Poisson ¹	PNP, PNW	
12	t_Function ¹	TPW, PTW, PTD	tVTLG, F06_, F02, F06, F03Z
13	x2_Function ¹	XPW, PXW, PXD	ch2VTLG, F07_, F02, F07, F03Z
14	z_Dichte ¹	DZW, ZDW	
15	z_Function ¹	ZPW, PZW, PZD	NVTLG, E01, F02, F03
16	Theta ²		
17	Theta_Q ²		
18	Theta_Qv ²		
19	Theta_RQ ²		
20	Theta_S ²		
21	Verteilungsform		
22	Verteilungsform_2u		
23	Verteilungsform_kor		

¹) implemented in FunktionWin (Schrausser, 2023f, 2025c).

²) implemented in ThetaWin (Schrausser, 2023g, 2025a).

2. ConsoleApp_EEG

Console applications (c.f. Schrausser, 2024b) for EEG (s. Galvani, 1791; Caton, 1875; Beck, 1890 and Berger, 1929) parameters implemented in ATINA (Schrausser, 2006), calculating coherence (2.1.; c.f. French & Graham, 1984; Schrausser et al., 2001; Guevara et al., 2011; Puthanmadam Subramaniam & Thiagarajan, 2025), cross correlation (2.2.) and focus parameters (2.3.-2.6.; s. Schrausser, 2000a, b) from Fourier-analyzed data (c.f. Fourier, 1822). More profound insight into the methods is provided by e.g. Gerthsen (1966), Kumar and Bhuvanawari (2012), Siuly et al. (2017), Panov (2024), Grafakos (2024), Panitz et al. (2024), Brigola (2025) or Meschede et al. (2026).

For the implementation of the methods in the fields of neuropsychology or psychobiology see e.g. Neubauer et al. (2002), Neubauer et al. (2005), Micheloyannis et al. (2006), Neubauer and Fink (2009), Chiarionet et al. (2023), Zhang et al. (2023) or Nguyen et al. (2025), c.f. further Adrian (2016), Tassinari (2019) and Rossini et al. (2025).

2.1. ERC, ERCX

Calculates event related coherence ERC, where coherence

$$Coh_{xy}^2 = \frac{P_{xy}^2(f)}{P_{xx}(f) \cdot P_{yy}(f)},$$

with cross power P_{xy} within given frequency f in \mathbb{C} defined by

$$P_{xy}(f) = \Re(a_{xy})^2 + \Im(a_{xy})^2,$$

c.f. Schrausser (2000b).

Usage:

```

erc [input][output][nCOH][nX][refs][refe][acts][acte][typ]
[input] ..... Input File, Format ASCII tab. (e.g. coh.asc)
[output] ..... Output File
[nCOH] ..... Number of coherence values
[nX] ..... Number of channel combinations
[refs] ..... Number of reference start value
[refe] ..... Number of reference end value
[acts] ..... Number of active start value
[acte] ..... Number of active end value
[typ] ..... Type of output (0):individual (1):append

```

2.2. XCOR

Calculates cross correlation xCOR.

Usage:

```
xcor [input][output][n][k]
[input] ..... Input File, Format ASCII tab. (e.g. data.dat)
[output] .... Output File
[n] ..... Number of cases
[k] ..... Number of variables
```

2.3. FOC

Calculates *focus* parameter yf , where

$$yf = \sum_{i=1}^k 1 - \frac{x_i - x_{min}}{d},$$

with

$$d = x_{max} - x_{min}.$$

Usage:

```
foc [input][output][n][k]
[input] ..... Input File, Format ASCII tab. (e.g. data.dat)
[output] .... Output File
[n] ..... Number of cases
[k] ..... Number of leads
```

2.4. DIS

Reading in *distance* values d_{ij} for x_i, x_j and calculates *wights* g_{ij} defined by

$$g_{ij} = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{d_{ij}}}.$$

Usage:

```
dis [input][output][n][k]
[input] ..... Input File, Format ASCII tab.
[output] .... Output File
[n] ..... Number of cases
[k] ..... Number of leads
```

2.5. FLOC

Calculates *spatial focus* parameter $yloc$, where

$$yloc = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \frac{1}{G_i} \cdot \left[\left(1 - \frac{x_i - x_{min}}{d} \right) \cdot w_{G_{ij}} \right]}{k-2},$$

with

$$G_i = \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} g_{ij},$$

$$w_{G_{ij}} = g_{ij} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{x_j - x_{min}}{d} \right).$$

Usage:

```
floc [input][output][n][k][distance]
[input] ..... Input File, Format ASCII tab. (e.g. data.dat)
[output] .... Output File
[n] ..... Number of cases
[k] ..... Number of leads
[distance] .. Distance Matrix File
```

2.6. OUT

Generates output file.

Usage:

```
out [input][n][k][start][end]
[input] ..... Input File, Format ASCII tab. (e.g. coh.asc)
[n] ..... Number of values / cases / rows
[k] ..... Number of variables / columns
[start] ..... Number of block start value
[end] ..... Number of block end value
```

3. ConsoleApp_Integral

Console applications for *integral* and *interpolation* (see Schrausser, 2023b). For the basic concept of *Riemann sums* (Riemann, 1868), see Lewis et al. (1978), Hassler (2007), Truc (2019), Torchinsky (2022), Forster and Lindemann (2023), further Goel and Rodriguez (1987), Guillemin and Stroock (2008), Büchter and Henn (2010), for *integral calculus* in general see Schwarz (1997), Meyberg and Vachenaer (2001a), Allen and Isaacson (2019) or Neher (2024).

The included methods are as follows:

(3.1.-3.2.) *Romberg's method* (Romberg, 1955) as an analytical method for achieving higher approximation accuracy for integrals, based on the *Richardson extrapolation* (Richardson, 1911; s. Rannacher, 1987; Bickel & Yahav, 1988; Sidi, 1988, 2003; Dubeau, 2019; Bach, 2021) or the *trapezoidal rule* (c.f. Luke et al., 1969; Abdulhameed & Memon, 2021; Izzo et al., 2022; Bujang, 2025), respectively. The *Richardson extrapolation* is further used, for example, in machine learning and other fields to *accelerate* convergences. In this context c.f. Herrmann (1983), Jetter (1984), Talay and Tubaro (1990), von Petersdorff (1993) or Meyberg and Vachenaer (2001b, p. 209).

(3.3.-3.4.) the *Cubic spline* interpolation (Schoenberg, 1946; c.f. Rabut, 1992; Agarwal & Wong, 1993; Farin, 1994) as a method for *polynomial curve fitting* and precise interpolation of *empirical* data points, where the rate of change corresponds to the slope, resulting in smooth, continuous function curves. See in this context Cheng and Barsky (1991), Fredenhagen et al. (1999), Jiang and Zhao (2009), Moon (2001), Sarfraz (2008), Sun et al. (2023), Török et al. (2025), Jarre (2025, 2026). For application in *EEG* examination and psychophysiology, see e.g. Perrin et al. (1987), Soufflet et al. (1991), Congedo et al. (2002), Roy and Shukla (2017), Abduganiev et al. (2023) or Schulter et al. (2023, p. 5).

(3.5.-3.6.) the *Newton* interpolation (Cardano, 1545; Newton, 1687) as a further method for *curve fitting* which is easier to calculate, however, has lower accuracy and stability compared to interpolation via *cubic splines*, calculates a significantly less smooth curve and is therefore better suited for *smaller* datasets and lower accuracy requirements. For an overview c.f. Rutishauser (1990), Scherer (2010) or Epperson (2021), further insight give e.g. Tsao (1977) and Zou et al. (2020).

3.1. ROMI

Approximates (i) *surface* or (ii) *curve integrals* [Approximiert (i) Flächen- oder (ii) Kurven-Integrale]

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx$$

by means of the *Romberg method*, if applicable including file output to **romi.txt** from the function *matrix* [mittels *Romberg Methode*, dabei ggf. *Dateiausgabe nach romi.txt von Funktionsmatrix*]

$$F = (x|y),$$

where [bei]

$$x = \frac{x+d}{2}, y = \int_a^b f(x) dx.$$

- Execution of **ROMI.bat**:
- Definition of $f(x)$ in **ROMI.h**;
- Compiling **ROMI.c**;
- Execution of **ROMI.exe**.

- [Ausführung von **ROMI.bat**:]
- [Definition von $f(x)$ in **ROMI.h**:]

- [Compilieren von ROMI.c;]
- [Ausführung von ROMI.exe.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
ROMI [a][b][d][m][F]
[a] ..... Integration Minimum a
[b] ..... Integration Maximum b
[d] ..... Delta d
[m] ..... Mode (0):Area.I (1):Curve.I
[F] ..... Function matrix (0):none (1):romi.txt
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
ROMI.bat
ROMI 1 10 0.0001 0 0
ROMI -9 0 0.5 0 1
```

3.2. ROME

Approximates $\int_a^b f(x)dx$ using Romberg extrapolation [Approximiert $\int_a^b f(x)dx$ mittels Romberg-Extrapolation] (see. Meyberg & Vachenaue, 2001b, p. 209).

- Execution of **ROME.bat**:
- Definition of $f(x)$ in **ROME.h**;
- Compiling **ROME.c**;
- Execution of **ROME.exe**.

- [Ausführung von ROME.bat:]
- [Definition von $f(x)$ in ROME.h:]
- [Compilieren von ROME.c:]
- [Ausführung von ROME.exe.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
ROME [a][b]
[a] ..... Integration Minimum a
[b] ..... Integration Maximum b
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
ROME.bat
ROME 1 10
ROME -14 1
```

3.3. KUSI

Cubic spline interpolation: Calculation of the coefficient matrix $A = (b|c|d)$ and $s(x)$ for an (empirical) function matrix $F = (x|y)$, where [Kubische Spline Interpolation: Berechnung der Koeffizientenmatrix $A = (b|c|d)$ sowie $s(x)$ zu einer (empirischen) Funktionsmatrix $F = (x|y)$, wobei]

$$s_i(x) = y_i + b_i \cdot (x - x_i) + c_i \cdot (x - x_i)^2 + d_i \cdot (x - x_i)^3; i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

- Import of an ASCII function matrix file **F**;
 - Output of the ASCII coefficient matrix file **A (KUSI.txt)**;
 - Calculation of $s(x)$ via the interpolation function.
- [Übernahme einer ASCII Funktionsmatrix Datei F;]
 - [Ausgabe der ASCII Koeffizientenmatrix Datei A (KUSI.txt);]
 - [Berechnung von $s(x)$ über die Interpolations-Funktion.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
KUSI [f][x]
[f] ..... Function matrix file (F)
[x] ..... Function value x
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
KUSI in.txt 0.5
```

3.4. KUSF

Cubic spline function: Calculation of a function matrix $S = (x|s(x))$ corresponding to coefficient matrix $A = (b|c|d)$, where [Kubische Spline Funktion: Berechnung einer Funktionsmatrix $S = (x|s(x))$ zu Koeffizientenmatrix $A = (b|c|d)$, wobei]

$$s_i(x) = y_i + b_i \cdot (x - x_i) + c_i \cdot (x - x_i)^2 + d_i \cdot (x - x_i)^3; i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

- Import of an ASCII function matrix file **F**;
- Import of the ASCII coefficient matrix file **A (KUSI.txt)**;
- Output of the ASCII function matrix file **S (KUSF.txt)**.

- [Übernahme einer ASCII Funktionsmatrix Datei F;]
- [Übernahme der ASCII Koeffizientenmatrix Datei A (KUSI.txt);]
- [Ausgabe der ASCII Funktionsmatrix Datei S (KUSF.txt).]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
KUSF [f][a][b][d]
[f] ..... Function matrix file (F)
[a] ..... (x) Minimum
[b] ..... (x) Maximum
[d] ..... Interval d
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
KUSF in.txt 1 10 0.1
```

3.5. NWTI

Newton interpolation: Calculation of the coefficient vector a as well as $p(x)$ for an (empirical) function matrix $F = (x|y)$, where [Newton Interpolation: Berechnung des Koeffizientenvektors a sowie $p(x)$ zu einer (empirischen) Funktionsmatrix $F = (x|y)$, wobei]

$$p(x) = a_0 + a_1 \cdot (x - 1) + a_2 \cdot (x - 1) \cdot (x - 2) \dots a_n \cdot (x - 1) \cdot (x - 2) \dots (x - n).$$

- Import of an ASCII function matrix file **F**;
- Output of the ASCII coefficient vector file **a (nwti.txt)**;
- Calculation of $p(x)$ using the interpolation polynomial.

- [Übernahme einer ASCII Funktionsmatrix Datei F;]
- [Ausgabe einer ASCII Koeffizientenvektor Datei a (nwti.txt);]
- [Berechnung von $p(x)$ über das Interpolations-Polynom.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
NWTI [f][x]
[f] ..... Function matrix file (F)
[x] ..... Function value x
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
NWTI in.txt 3
```

3.6. NWTP

Newton Interpolation Polynomial: Calculation of a function matrix $F = (x|p(x))$ corresponding to coefficient vector a , where [Newton Interpolations Polynom: Berechnung einer Funktionsmatrix $F = (x|p(x))$ zu Koeffizientenvektor a , wobei]

$$p(x) = a_0 + a_1 \cdot (x - 1) + a_2 \cdot (x - 1) \cdot (x - 2) \dots a_n \cdot (x - 1) \cdot (x - 2) \dots (x - n).$$

- Import of the ASCII coefficient vector file **a (nwti.txt)**;
- Output of the ASCII function matrix file **F (nwtp.txt)**.

- [Übernahme der ASCII Koeffizientenvektor Datei a (nwti.txt);]
- [Ausgabe der ASCII Funktionsmatrix Datei F (nwtp.txt).]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
NWTP [a][b][d]
[a] ..... (x) Minimum
[b] ..... (x) Maximum
[d] ..... Interval d
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
NWTP 1 10 0.1
```

4. ConsoleApp_Matrix

Console applications for (4.1.-4.9.) *matrix* calculation (Cayley, 1858; c.f. Cardano, 1545; Heisenberg, 1925; Turing, 1948 or Crilly, 1986) and (4.10.-4.21.) *tools*, s. Schrausser (2023c); on the topic in general c.f. Meyberg and Vachener (2001), Grcar (2011), Karpfinger (2022a, b), Shores (2018), Gentle (2024) or Saff and Snider (2025).

4.1. AMA

Adds or subtracts 2 *matrices*, with given [Addiert oder subtrahiert 2 Matrizen],

$$k_1 = k_2, n_1 = n_2.$$

[wird vorausgesetzt].

- Import of 2 ASCII matrix files.
 - Output of an ASCII matrix file.
- [Übernahme 2er ASCII Matrixdateien.]
 - [Ausgabe einer ASCII Matrixdatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
AMA [matrix1][matrix2][output][mode]
[matrix1] ... Input file 1
[matrix2] ... Input file 2
[output] .... Output file
[mode] ..... (0):Addition (1):Subtraction
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
AMA in1.txt in2.txt out.txt 0
```

4.2. IMA

Calculates the inverse A^{-1} of A using the *chained* form of *Gaussian elimination* [Berechnet die inverse A^{-1} von A über die verkettete Form des Gaußschen Algorithmus],

$$k_{max} = n_{max} = 200, a_{11} \neq 0.$$

This results in two triangular *matrices* B and C , as well as the *matrix* T to the generated identity *matrix* E ; A^{-1} is obtained by its transpose [Es resultieren 2 Dreiecksmatrizen B und C , sowie die Matrix T zur erzeugten Einheitsmatrix E , A^{-1} entsteht transponiert]:

```

. . . A 1 0 0 E
. . .   0 1 0
. . .   0 0 1

. . . B . . . T
. . .   . . .
. . .   . . .
. . .   . . .

. . . C
. . .

. . . (1/A)'
. . .
. . .
```

- Import of a square ASCII matrix file.
 - Output of a square ASCII matrix file.
- [Übernahme einer quadratischen ASCII Matrixdatei.]

- [Ausgabe einer quadratischen ASCII Matrixdatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
IMA [matrix][output]
[matrix] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
IMA in.txt out.txt
```

4.3. MMA

Multiplies two *matrices* ($k_1 = n_2$ is assumed). The result is a *matrix* with [Multipliziert 2 Matrizen ($k_1 = n_2$ wird vorausgesetzt). Es resultiert eine Matrix mit]

$$n = n_1, k = k_2:$$

```

      *      =
o . . o o   o o
o . . . .   o .
      . .
o . . o o   o o
o . . . .   o .
o . . . .   o .
o . . . .   o .
o . . . .   o .
o . . o o o o o o o o o
o . . . . . . . . o . . . .
      . . . . .
```

- Import of 2 ASCII matrix files.
 - Output of an ASCII matrix file.
- [Übernahme 2er ASCII Matrixdateien.]
 - [Ausgabe einer ASCII Matrixdatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
MMA [matrix1][matrix2][output]
[matrix1] ..... Input file 1
[matrix2] ..... Input file 2
[output] ..... Output file
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
MMA m1.txt m2.txt m3.txt
```

4.4. QMA

Squaring a square *matrix* [Quadratiert eine quadratische Matrix]:

```

      *      =
o . o o   o o
o . . .   o .
```

- Import of a square ASCII matrix file.
 - Output of a square ASCII matrix file.
- [Übernahme einer quadratischen ASCII Matrixdateien.]
 - [Ausgabe einer quadratischen ASCII Matrixdatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
QMA [matrix][output]
[matrix] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
QMA a.txt b.txt
```

4.5. SMA

Selects a *submatrix* (or *vector*) from a *matrix* [Selegiert eine Sub Matrix (oder einen Vektor) aus einer Matrix].

- Importing an ASCII matrix file.
- Output of an ASCII (matrix) file.
- [Übernahme einer ASCII Matrixdatei.]
- [Ausgabe einer ASCII (Matrix-)Datei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
SMA [matrix][output][i0][i1][j0][j1]
[matrix] ..... Matrix file
[output] ..... Matrix output file
[i0] ..... From line
[i1] ..... To line
[j0] ..... From column
[j1] ..... To column
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
SMA in.txt out1.txt 1 5 2 2 //Columnvector j2
SMA in.txt out2.txt 2 2 1 5 //Linevector i2
SMA in.txt out3.txt 2 4 2 4 //Submatrix
SMA in.txt out4.txt 3 3 3 3 //Single number
```

4.6. SPUR

Calculates the trace (*sp*) of a square *matrix A* [Berechnet die Spur (*sp*) einer quadratischen Matrix A]:

```
o . . . A
. o .
. . o
. . .
      sp A
```

- Import of a square ASCII matrix file.
- Output of *sp A* in file *SPUR.txt*.
- [Übernahme einer quadratischen ASCII Matrixdatei.]
- [Ausgabe von *sp A* in die Datei *SPUR.txt*.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
SPUR [matrix][mode]
[matrix] ..... Input file
[mode] ..... Mode of trace calculation:
(0):Addition (Standard)
(1):Multiplication (s. VMA.exe)
(2):Subtraction
(3):Division
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
SPUR in.txt 0
```

4.7. TRP

Transposes a data *matrix* [Transponiert eine Datenmatrix],

$$n_{max} = k_{max} = 1299.$$

Column separator, input file: tab or space. Column separator, output file: 1 space [Spaltentrennzeichen, Eingabedatei: Tabulator oder Leerzeichen. Spaltentrennzeichen, Ausgabedatei: 1 Leerzeichen].

- Importing an ASCII data matrix file.
- Output of a transposed ASCII data matrix file.
- [Übernahme einer ASCII Datenmatrixdatei.]
- [Ausgabe einer transponierten ASCII Datenmatrixdatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
TRP [input][output]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
TRP in.txt out.txt
```

4.8. VMA

Calculates the *chained form of Gaussian elimination* of a square *matrix A*, with [Berechnet die verkettete Form des Gaußschen Algorithmus einer quadratischen Matrix A, mit]

$$k_{max} = n_{max} = 250, a_{11} \neq 0.$$

This results in two triangular matrices *B* and *C* [Es resultieren 2 Dreiecksmatrizen B und C]:

```
      . . . A
      . . .
      . . .
      . . . B
      . . .
      . . . C
      . . .
```

The determinant of *A* ($\det A$) is the product of the elements in the main diagonal of *B* ($\prod b_{ii}$) [Die Determinante von A ($\det A$) ist das Produkt der Elemente in der Hauptdiagonale von B ($\prod b_{ii}$)].

- Import of a square ASCII matrix file.
- Output of a square ASCII matrix file.
- [Übernahme einer quadratischen ASCII Matrixdatei.]
- [Ausgabe einer quadratischen ASCII Matrixdatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
VMA [matrix][output]
[matrix] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
VMA in.txt out.txt
```

4.9. ZMA

Multiplies a *matrix* by a real number [Multipliziert eine Matrix mit einer reellen Zahl].

- Import of an ASCII matrix file.
- Output of an ASCII matrix file.
- [Übernahme einer ASCII Matrixdatei.]
- [Ausgabe einer ASCII Matrixdatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
ZMA [matrix][output][wert]
[matrix] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[wert] ..... Real number
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
ZMA in.txt out.txt 3
```

4.10. ENT

Performs a symmetrical interlaced split of a data vector file x_0 [Führt eine symmetrische entwobene Aufteilung einer Datenvektordatei x_0 durch]:

```
x0
--
1
2
3
4

x1 x2
-- --
1   2
3   4
```

- Importing a single-column ASCII file.
- Output of 2 single-column ASCII files.
- [Übernahme einer einspaltigen ASCII Datei.]
- [Ausgabe von 2 einspaltigen ASCII Dateien.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
ENT [input][output1][output2]
[input] ..... Input file
[output1] .... Output file 1
[output2] .... Output file 2
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
ENT in.txt out1.txt out2.txt
```

4.11. KTF

Reduces or increases the size of a perfectly linear data vector. The data adjustment up to n' is iteratively performed by [Verringert oder vergrößert den Umfang eines perfekt linearen Datenvektors. Die bis n' iterative Datenanpassung erfolgt über]

$$x_i[n] = x_i[n+1] \cdot \frac{n}{n-1}; n' < n,$$
$$x_i[n] = x_i[n-1] \cdot \frac{n-2}{n-1}; n' > n.$$

- Import of a single-column, ascendingly ordered ASCII data vector file of size n .
- Output of a single-column, ascendingly ordered ASCII data vector file of size n' .
- [Übernahme einer einspaltigen, aufsteigend geordneten ASCII Datenvektordatei im Umfang n .]
- [Ausgabe einer einspaltigen, aufsteigend geordneten ASCII Datenvektordatei im Umfang n' .]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
ktf [input][output][n]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[n] ..... Vector size  $n'$ 
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
ktf data_in.txt data_out.txt 30
```

4.12. KTF2

Reduces or increases the size of a data vector [Verringert oder vergrößert den Umfang eines Datenvektors] ($n_{max} = n'_{max} = 33000$).

- Import of a single-column, ascendingly ordered ASCII data vector file of size n .

- Output of a single-column, ascendingly ordered ASCII data vector file of size n' .
- [Übernahme einer einspaltigen, aufsteigend geordneten ASCII Datenvektordatei im Umfang n .]
- [Ausgabe einer einspaltigen, aufsteigend geordneten ASCII Datenvektordatei im Umfang n' .]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
ktf2 [input][output][n]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[n] ..... Vector size  $n'$ 
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
ktf2 in.txt out.txt 12
ktf2 in.txt out.txt 110
```

4.13. KTF3

Adapts a data vector to a target coordinate system. The data adaptation is performed by [Passt einen Datenvektor an ein Ziel-Koordinatensystem an. Die Datenanpassung erfolgt über]

$$x'_i = \min_x + \{[(\min_x - x_{min}) - (\min_x - x_i)] \cdot \frac{\max_x - \min_x}{(\min_x - x_{min}) - (\min_x - x_{max})}\}$$

When inverting a value, x''_i is calculated as [bei einer Wertinvertierung errechnet man x''_i über]

$$x''_i = (\min_x + \max_x) - x'_i,$$

where [mit]

\min_x Value of the minimum point in the target coordinate system
 \max_x Value of the maximum point in the target coordinate system
 x_{min} Vector minimum value
 x_{max} Vector maximum value

\min_x [Wert des Minimalpunktes im Ziel-Koordinatensystem]
 \max_x [Wert des Maximalpunktes im Ziel-Koordinatensystem]
 x_{min} [Vektor Minimalwert]
 x_{max} [Vektor Maximalwert]

- Import of a single-column, ascendingly ordered ASCII data vector file.
- Output of a two-column, ascendingly ordered ASCII data matrix file containing:
 - [Übernahme einer einspaltigen, aufsteigend geordneten ASCII Datenvektordatei.]
 - [Ausgabe einer zweispaltigen, aufsteigend geordneten ASCII Datenmatrixdatei beinhaltend:]

The data vector adapted to the target coordinate system; the initial data vector [Den an das Ziel-Koordinatensystem angepassten Datenvektor; den ursprünglichen Datenvektor].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
ktf3 [input][output][minx][maxx][inv]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[minx] ..... Val. of the min. point in the target coordinate system
[maxx] ..... Val. of the max. point in the target coordinate system
[inv] ..... (1):Value inversion (0):No Value inversion
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
ktf3 data_in.txt data_out.txt 1 100 1
ktf3 data_in.txt data_out.txt 371 51 0
```

4.14. NTF

Generates an ascending linear data vector and fits it to a target coordinate system. The data fitting is performed by [Erzeugt einen aufsteigend geordneten linearen Datenvektor und passt

diesen an ein Ziel-Koordinatensystem an. Die Datenanpassung erfolgt über

$$x'_i = \min_x + \left\{ \left[(\min_x - x_{\min}) - (\min_x - x_i) \right] \cdot \frac{\max_x - \min_x}{(\min_x - x_{\min}) - (\min_x - x_{\max})} \right\}$$

When inverting a value, x''_i is calculated as [bei einer Wertinver-
 tierung errechnet man x''_i über]

$$x''_i = (\min_x + \max_x) - x'_i,$$

where [mit]

\min_x Value of the minimum point in the target coordinate system
 \max_x Value of the maximum point in the target coordinate system
 x_{\min} Vector minimum value
 x_{\max} Vector maximum value

\min_x [Wert des Minimalpunktes im Ziel-Koordinatensystem]
 \max_x [Wert des Maximalpunktes im Ziel-Koordinatensystem]
 x_{\min} [Vektor Minimalwert]
 x_{\max} [Vektor Maximalwert]

- Output of a single-column, ascending linear ASCII data vector file.
- [Ausgabe einer einspaltigen, aufsteigend geordneten linearen ASCII Datenvektordatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
ntf [output][minn][maxn][min][max][inv]
[output] ..... Output file
[minn] ..... n Minimum value
[maxn] ..... n Maximum value
[min] ..... Coordinates Minimum Position Value
[max] ..... Coordinates Maximum Position Value
[inv] ..... (1):inverted (0):not inverted
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
ntf data_out.txt 1 30000 1 30000 0
ntf data_out.txt 1 30000 372 50 1
```

4.15. SEL

Selects a data vector from a data matrix [Selektiert einen Datenvektor aus einer Datenmatrix],

$$n_{\max} = 33000.$$

- Import of an ASCII data matrix file.
- Output of a single-column ASCII data vector file.
- [Übernahme einer ASCII Datenmatrixdatei.]
- [Ausgabe einer einspaltigen ASCII Datenvektordatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
sel [input][output][a][k]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[a] ..... Vector number
[k] ..... Number of vectors
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
sel in.txt out.asc 3 5
```

4.16. SRT

Sorts a data vector [Sortiert einen Datenvektor],

$$n_{\max} = 33000,$$

16-digit output [16 stellige Ausgabe].

- Import of a single-column ASCII data vector file.
- Output of a sorted single-column ASCII data vector file.
- [Übernahme einer einspaltigen ASCII Datenvektordatei.]
- [Ausgabe einer sortierten einspaltigen ASCII Datenvektordatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
srt [input][output] [[d]]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[d] ..... optional (1):descending sorting
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
srt in.txt out.txt
srt in.txt out.txt 1
```

4.17. SRT1

Concatenates two sorted data vectors using filestream processing [Verkettet 2 sortierte Datenvektoren mit Filestream Verarbeitung],

$$n_{\max} \rightarrow \infty.$$

- Import of two ascendingly sorted single-column ASCII data vector files.
- Output of a sorted single-column ASCII file vector file.
- [Übernahme von zwei aufsteigend sortierten einspaltigen ASCII Datenvektordateien.]
- [Ausgabe einer sortierten einspaltigen ASCII Datenvektordatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
srt1 [input1][input2][output]
[input1] ..... Input file 1
[input2] ..... Input file 2
[output] ..... Output file
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
srt1 in1.asc in2.asc out.asc
```

4.18. SRT2

Sorts a data vector [Sortiert einen Datenvektor],

$$n_{\max} = 33000.$$

Data sorting is performed via iterative pairwise comparison [Die Datensortierung erfolgt über iterativen Paarvergleich]

$$i \text{ vs. } i + 1$$

and pairwise exchange [und Paartausch]

$$i > i + 1.$$

(slower than SRT.EXE) [(langsamer als SRT.EXE)].

- Import of a single-column ASCII data vector file.
- Output of a sorted single-column ASCII data vector file.
- [Übernahme einer einspaltigen ASCII Datenvektordatei.]
- [Ausgabe einer sortierten einspaltigen ASCII Datenvektordatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
srt2 [input][output] [[d]]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[d] ..... optional (1):descending sorting
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
srt2 in.txt out.txt
srt2 in.txt out.txt 1
```

4.19. SRT3

Sorts a data vector [Sortiert einen Datenvektor],

$$n_{\max} = 33000,$$

max. 8 digits [max. 8-Stellen].

Very fast calculation through implementation of the C-function **Qsort** [Sehr schnelle Berechnung durch Umsetzung der C-eigenen Qsort Funktion].

- Import of a single-column ASCII data vector file.
- Output of a sorted single-column ASCII data vector file.
- [Übernahme einer einspaltigen ASCII Datenvektordatei.]
- [Ausgabe einer sortierten einspaltigen ASCII Datenvektordatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
srt3 [input][output] [[d]]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[d] ..... optional (1):descending sorting
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
srt3 in.txt out.txt
srt3 in.txt out.txt 1
```

4.20. V2V

Concatenates two single-column ASCII files ($n_1 = n_2$ required) [Fügt 2 einspaltige ASCII Dateien aneinander ($n_1 = n_2$ wird vorausgesetzt)].

- Import of 2 single-column ASCII files.
- Output of a two-column ASCII file.
- [Übernahme von 2 einspaltigen ASCII Dateien.]
- [Ausgabe einer zweispaltigen ASCII Datei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
V2V [input1][input2][output][tab]
[input1] ..... Input file 1
[input2] ..... Input file 2
[output] ..... Output file
[tab] ..... Column separator
(0):Tabulator
(1):Blank
(*):String
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
V2V in1.txt in2.txt out.txt 1
V2V in1.txt in2.txt out.txt <---->
```

4.21. Z2Z

Concatenates two ASCII files [Fügt zwei ASCII Dateien aneinander].

- Import of two ASCII files.
- Output of an ASCII file.
- [Übernahme zweier ASCII Dateien.]
- [Ausgabe einer ASCII Datei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
Z2Z [input1][input2][output]
[input1] ..... Input file 1
[input2] ..... Input file 2
[output] ..... Output file
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
Z2Z in1.txt in2.txt out.txt
```

Table 2. ConsoleApp functions overview with corresponding functions in SCHRAUSSER-MAT (Schrausser, 2022).

Category	chpt. nr.	Function	
		ConsoleApp	SCHRAUSSER-MAT
EEG/ Focus parameters	2 1	ERC, ERCX	
	2 2	XCOR	
	2 3	FOC ¹	
	2 4	DIS ¹	
	2 5	FLOC ¹	
	2 6	OUT ¹	
Integral/ Interpolation	3 1	ROMI	
	3 2	ROME	
	3 3	KUSI	
	3 4	KUSF	
	3 5	NWTI	
	3 6	NWTP	
Matrix/ Data manipulation	4 1	AMA	MXA, MXS
	4 2	IMA	MXI
	4 3	MMA	MXM
	4 4	QMA	MXQ
	4 5	SMA	
	4 6	SPUR	MSP
	4 7	TRP	MXT
	4 8	VMA	MXV
	4 9	ZMA	
	4 10	ENT	
4 11	KTF		
4 12	KTF2		
4 13	KTF3		
4 14	NTF		
4 15	SEL		
4 16	SRT		
4 17	SRT1		
4 18	SRT2		
4 19	SRT3		
4 20	V2V		
4 21	Z2Z		

¹) implemented in ATINA (Schrausser, 2006).

5. ConsoleApp_String

Console applications for string- and number-transformation, see Schrausser (2023d).

5.1. 2DEC

Converts the argument to a decimal number [Argument in Dezimalzahl].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
2DEC [x]
[x] ..... Argument
```

5.2. DEC2

Decimal number conversion [Dezimalzahl Umwandlung].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
DEC2 [d]
[d] ..... Decimal number
```

5.3. BIN2DEC

Binary number converted to decimal number [Binärzahl in Dezimalzahl].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
BIN2DEC [b]
[b] ..... Binary number
```

5.4. DEC2BIN

Binary number converted to decimal number [Dezimalzahl in Binärzahl].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
DEC2BIN [d]
[d] ..... Decimal number
```

5.5. ABCD

Modifies or deletes strings in an ASCII file [Ändert oder löscht Strings einer ASCII Datei].

- Import of an ASCII file.
- Output of a modified ASCII file.
- [Übernahme einer ASCII Datei.]
- [Ausgabe einer modifizierten ASCII Datei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
ABCD [input][output][ab][cd][sw]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[ab] ..... String to be modified
[cd] ..... String to be inserted
[sw] ..... (0):modifies
           (1):deletes (2):inserts a space
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
ABCD input.txt output.txt .txt .asc 0
ABCD input.txt output.txt REM 0 1
```

5.6. AZUBE

Changing individual characters in an ASCII file [Änderung einzelner Zeichen einer ASCII Datei].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
AZUBE [input][output][a][b]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[a] ..... Character
[b] ..... Modify
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
AZUBE input.txt output.txt , .
```

5.7. TEZUTE

Changing individual strings in a file [Änderung einzelner Strings einer Datei].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
TEZUTE [input][output][a][b]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[a] ..... String
[b] ..... Modify
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
78 00
67 8
null 00
9 null
```

```
TEZUTE input.txt output.txt null 00
```

```
78
00
67
8
00
00
9
00
```

Edit source code for formatted output [Zur formatierten Ausgabe Quellcode bearbeiten].

5.8. AB_L

Inserts a string (i) before and/or a string (ii) after each line of a file [Fügt einen String (i) vor und/oder einen String (ii) nach jeder Zeile einer Datei ein].

- Import of a single-column ASCII file.
- Output of a (one-,) two- or three-column ASCII file.
- [Übernahme einer einspaltigen ASCII Datei.]
- [Ausgabe einer (ein-,) zwei- oder dreispaltigen ASCII Datei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
AB_L [input][output][a][sw][z][sw]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
[a] ..... String inserted before each line of input file
[sw] ..... (0):no insert before each line
[z] ..... String inserted after each line of input file
[sw] ..... (0):no insert after each line
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
AB_L in.txt out.txt move 1 verzeichnis 1
AB_L in.txt out.txt del 1 0 0
```

5.9. BIIA

Encodes a file into an ASCII file (recoding via AIIB.EXE) [Encodiert eine Datei in eine ASCII Datei (Recodierung via AIIB.EXE)].

- Import of a file.
- Output of an encoded ASCII file (*.bii).
- [Übernahme einer Datei.]
- [Ausgabe einer encodierten ASCII Datei (*.bii).]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
BIIA [input][output][mode][form]
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file in ASCII format (*.bii)
[mode] ..... (1):cd01 SCHRAUSSER CODE, uppercase letter combination
              (2 characters, e.g. AA, FD, ..., good readability -
              unambiguous, for archiving)
              (2):cd02 SCHRAUSSER CODE, keyboard character comb.
              (1 or 2 characters, e.g. a, 1A, ..., small file)
              (3):cd03 SCHRAUSSER CODE, number combination (3 characters,
              e.g. 001, 123, ..., optimal readability)
              (4):cd04 SCHRAUSSER CODE, ASCII-combination (1 or 2
              characters, e.g. -, #+, ..., minimum file size)
              (5):HEX Hexadecimal value - No AIIB recoding
              (6):DEZ Decimal value
              (7):OKT Octal value - No AIIB recoding
              (8):ASCII characters directly - No AIIB recoding
[form] ..... (1):1-column ASCII output
              (2):1-line ASCII output in block format without breaks
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
BIIA bild.jpg bild.bii 4 2
```

5.10. AIIB

Recodes a SCHRAUSSER CODE or decimal encoded file (encoding via BIIA.EXE) [Recodiert eine SCHRAUSSER CODE oder dezimal encodierte Datei (Encodierung via BIIA.EXE)].

- Importing a SCHRAUSSER CODE file (*.bii).
- Output of the recoded original file.
- [Übernahme einer SCHRAUSSER CODE Datei (*.bii).]
- [Ausgabe der recodierten Ursprungsdatei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
AIIB [input]
[input] ..... SCHRAUSSER CODE file
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
AIIB bild.bii
```

5.11. STGERSETZ

Modification of one or more *substrings* (single characters or *strings*) in a contiguous *string* (without spaces), read as a line of an ASCII file [Änderung ein oder mehrerer Substrings (Einzelzeichen oder Zeichenketten) in einem zusammenhängenden String (ohne Leerzeichen), eingelesen als Zeile einer ASCII Datei].

- Importing a line from an ASCII file.
- [Übernahme einer Zeile aus einem ASCII-File.]

Example [Bsp.]:

```
12345678
abcdefghijk
ABCDEF
1234567890
```

- Line-by-line processing of the *strings* and output to an ASCII file.
- [zeilenweise Bearbeitung der Strings und Ausgabe in ein ASCII-File.]

The processing steps are logged in *stgersez_log.txt* [Die Bearbeitungsschritte werden in *stgersez_log.txt* protokolliert].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
STGERSETZ [input][output][typ][alt][neu]
[input] ..... Input file (strings line by line)
[output] ..... Output file (strings line by line)
[typ] ..... (0):deletes
           (1):modifies
           (2):insert a space
[alt] ..... String to be modified
[neu] ..... Change to string
```

The type of argument [neu] has no effect on [typ] (0) *delete* and (2) *insert a space*, but must be specified as character (e.g. '-'). A space in the input file splits the *string* and results in a new line in the output file. Some special characters are ignored [Die Art des Arguments [neu] hat für [typ] (0) löschen und (2) ein Leerzeichen einfügen keine Auswirkung, muss aber als beliebiges Zeichen angegeben werden (iuF. '-'). Ein Leerzeichen in der Eingabedatei trennt die Zeichenkette und führt zu einer neuen Zeile in der Ausgabedatei. Manche Sonderzeichen bleiben unberücksichtigt].

Example [Bsp.]:

```
STGERSETZ input.txt output.txt 0 8 - //deletes 8
```

```
1234567
abcdefghijk
ABCDEF
123456790
```

```
STGERSETZ input.txt output.txt 1 def DEF //changes def to DEF
```

```
12345678
abcDEFghijk
ABCDEF
1234567890
```

```
STGERSETZ input.txt output.txt 2 234 - //inserts a space for 234
```

```
1 5678
abcdefghijk
ABCDEF
1 567890
```

6. ConsoleApp_Tools

Console *tool* applications, see Schrausser (2023e).

6.1. AUTO

Creates a C-source file and directory structure.

- Declaration of parameters (*name, filestreams, loops*).
- Creation of framework-file **NAME.c** as specified.
- Creation of ASCII framework-file **NOTE_NAME.txt**.

Directory structure:

```
_NAME_\NAME.c
_NAME_\debug\NOTE_NAME.txt
DOSCOM.exe
```

Usage:

```
AUTO [name][input][output][n1][L]
[name] ..... C projekt mame
[input] ..... ASCII input filename
[output] ..... ASCII output filename
[n1] ..... Number of loop-shells to implement
[L] ..... Language (0):English (1):German
```

Example:

```
AUTO TEST 0 0 0 0
AUTO PR01 input.txt output.txt 3 1
AUTO PR02 0 output.txt 1 0
```

6.2. DLS

Writes a file to the console [Schreibt eine Datei zur Konsole].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
DLS [input] [ [i][m1][m2] ]
[input] ..... Input file
optional:
[i] ..... (1):displays file name, n, k, m1, m2, i, j
           (0):displays no additional information
[m1] ..... Start line of text output
[m2] ..... End line of text output
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
DLS NOTIZ_DLS.txt
DLS NOTIZ_DLS.txt 1
DLS NOTIZ_DLS.txt 1 1
DLS NOTIZ_DLS.txt 0 3 10
DLS NOTIZ_DLS.txt 1 10 10
```

6.3. FIL

Writes a list of all specified files in the current directory to an ASCII file [Schreibt eine Liste aller spezifizierten Dateien des aktuellen Verzeichnisses in eine ASCII Datei].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
FIL [output][*]
[output] ..... Output file
[*] ..... File specification
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
FIL dir.txt *.*
```

6.4. KOPIE

Copies a file [Kopiert eine Datei].

- Import of a file.
- Output of a copy of a file (if applicable modified).
- [Übernahme einer Datei.]
- [Ausgabe einer (ggf. modifizierten) Dateikopie.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
KOPIE [input][output] ([switch])
[input] ..... Input file
[output] ..... Output file
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
KOPIE DTREN.BAT DTRENA.BAT
```

6.5. SRC

Writes the command-line argument to an ASCII file [Schreibt das Kommandozeilenargument in eine ASCII Datei].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
SRC [output][typ][arg][sw]
[output] ..... Output file
[typ] ..... (0):attach (1):create
[arg] ..... Argument
[sw] ..... (0):line break (1):space (2):no character
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
SRC out.bat 1 lsn 1
SRC out.bat 0 nul.txt 0
```

6.6. T

Inserts the command-line arguments into the ASCII file **T.txt**. The arguments are separated by a space [Fügt die Kommandozeilenargumente in die ASCII Datei T.txt ein. Die Argumente werden in der Datei durch ein Leerzeichen getrennt].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
T [argi]..[argn]
[argi] ..... String
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
T This is a very simple program
T for fast text input into a file.
T Das ist ein sehr einfaches Programm
T zur schnellen Texteingabe in eine Datei.
```

6.7. DOSCOM

Starts a DOS shell in the current directory. Copies itself to the directory **_DOSCOM**, which is linked to the desktop. Renames to **nil** after use in the current directory [Startet eine DOS-Shell im aktuellen Verzeichnis. Kopiert sich selbst in das mit dem Desktop verknüpfte Verzeichnis **_DOSCOM**. Umbenennung in **nil** nach Gebrauch im aktuellen Verzeichnis].

Usage [Handhabung]:

Drag the desktop shortcut **_DOSCOM** to any directory, run it there, and delete it after use [Aus der Desktopverknüpfung **_DOSCOM** in ein beliebiges Verzeichnis ziehen, dort ausführen und nach Gebrauch löschen].

6.8. FINDE

Search and find files [Dateien suchen und finden].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
FINDE [file]
[file] ..... File to be found
```

6.9. LSN

Deletes a file [Löscht eine Datei].

- Input the name of a file to be deleted.

- [Übernahme des Namens einer zu löschenden Datei.]

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
LSN [file]
[file] ..... Filename
```

Example [Bsp.]:

```
LSN oo
```

6.10. CMND, CMNDw

Executes console commands with arguments [Führt Consolenbefehle mit Argumenten aus].

Usage [Handhabung]:

```
CMND [cmd]
[cmd] ..... Command

CMNDw [cmd][argc]
[cmd] ..... Command
[argc] ..... n of Arguments
```

Table 3. ConsoleApp tools overview.

Category	chpt.	nr.	Function
	5	1	2DEC
	5	2	DEC2
	5	3	BIN2DEC
	5	4	DEC2BIN
	5	5	ABCD
String/ Number	5	6	AZUBE
	5	7	TEZUTE
	5	8	AB_L
	5	9	BIIA
	5	10	AiIB
	5	11	STGERSETZ
	6	1	AUTO
	6	2	DLS
	6	3	FIL
	6	4	KOPIE
	6	5	SRC
Tools	6	6	T
	6	7	DOSCOM
	6	8	FINDE
	6	9	LSN
	6	10	CMND, CMNDw

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